

THE ROLE OF THE NATIONAL IDEAL IN THE RENEWED UZBEKISTAN

Sattorova D.F.

Tashkent State Dental Institute Social sciences with bioethics course
head of the Department

Yuldashev Temur

Stage 2 Master

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Abstract. The principle "for the sake of man" is becoming more and more priority in our lives. Consequently, this principle implies the creation of decent living conditions for every citizen living in our country, the glorification of human value in society. In the following years, large-scale updates were carried out in the medical system, as well as in all areas, with a special emphasis on strengthening the social protection of employees of the industry.

Key words: strong state, socio-political form, multinational states.

РОЛЬ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ИДЕАЛА В ОБНОВЛЕННОМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. Принцип «ради человека» становится все более приоритетным в нашей жизни. Следовательно, этот принцип подразумевает создание достойных условий жизни для каждого гражданина, проживающего в нашей стране, прославление ценности человека в обществе. В последующие годы были проведены масштабные обновления в системе медицины, а также во всех сферах, с особым акцентом на усиление социальной защиты работников отрасли.

Ключевые слова: сильное государство, общественно-политическая форма, многонациональные государства.

Purpose: in our opinion, the national ideal is a socio – ideological category that embodies a set of normative and moral values that serve the nationwide collective primacy of society in itself. It manifests itself as the main ideological desire of the nation in the direction of creativity. The national ideal is distinguished in the process of democratization and modernization of society by covering the normative and axiological directions of national development, the perfect sides of the creative strategy of national statehood and aspects of affiliation. The national ideal also represents the socio-political form of a "strong state" in itself. Therefore, it is necessary for our students to focus on it.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Uzbekistan falls under the umbrella of multinational states. We will have to organize our national progress so that we do not squeeze the actions, freedom of others. In essence, national development is determined by the freedom of a particular nation in determining its own path of development, new actions, opportunities, activities using various means. In carrying out such acts, people of certain nationalities, especially young people, strive to maintain their image even if they are inclined to be similar to others. True, everyone does it differently many absolutely cannot fail either. The successful life activity of such young people will depend not only on the situations in which they fall, but also on free will.

RESULT-DISCUSSION

Currently, due to human free will, each person can make different decisions and act differently in the same conditions. However, aspects of the life world of young people that have a

common meaning, aimed at understanding the national self, are a guarantee that they will coordinate and act together. If they do not recognize the common goals of their existence in this regard, then they risk creating individually and entering into other cultural values. Zero the general goals of any good change are in accordance with the relations that are formed in each state on the basis of local conditions and the peculiarities of the population. Therefore, in the absence of national philosophical considerations, common goals, ideals, norms and goals aimed at the realization of the national self, young people are deprived of the realization of the self. For example, scientist F.Ravshanov interprets the threats to spiritual progress today as: "spiritual vices, spiritual damage, spiritual abyss, ideological fanaticism, ideological parochialism, ideological stagnation, non-ideation, ideological aggression, ideological dependence". To understand and bring these to life, it is important to understand the national self, and in the formation of the national ideal, the general picture of human consciousness is expressed in the fact that each person seeks to live well and comfortably among his community.

Of particular importance in the development of the social ideal is the issue of national self-awareness. S.A. Atamurodov the ideal of understanding the national self "...special emphasis was placed on the fact that the affirmation of certain material and spiritual values as carriers consists in the understanding of belonging to language, culture, tradition, traditions and values". A.Abdurazzakov, on the other hand, pays special attention to the fact that "the perception of the national self is the level of folk spirituality, the development of its culture."

The appeal to philosophy in the promotion of the social ideal ensures the spiritual and cultural development of the spirit of each nation, exposes it to purge it of old creeds and stereotypes, to begin the paths of perspective corresponding to the goals of the present. In our opinion, social ideals are characterized by such noble goals as prosperous, prosperous people's lives of the land that they put before them. They have been living as noble ideas of the life of society since the time when humanity reached civilization. Such national ideals inherit our people from their ancestors. Humanity is always fighting evil in favor of good. The values embodied by the great ideals of the Uzbek people were influenced by different periods, in which the views of Abu Nasr Farabi, Ibn Sina, Amir Temur, Alisher Navai in particular occupy a special place.

Abu Nasr Farabi, in his "citizen politics", creates a doctrine with an ideal basis for his time by outlining his own views on a noble society, a just system. He is mature in all respects, promotes ideas about an ideal community that leads all residents to happiness, to science. Abu Nasr Farabi, in his book "The City of fertile people", wrote that "every human being is so structured by his nature that he will need a lot to live and achieve a high level of maturity. He alone cannot capture such things, he needs a human community to possess them. For this reason, it is necessary to convey to each other what is necessary to live," he writes. Phorobius calls for human cooperation, dreams of forming a single whole human community in the world.

In this work, Alloma does not dwell on such issues as moral education of the younger generation in what order, in particular focusing on what sensations the child has, but, by creating an abstract image of a person with ideal morals, puts forward the idea that it is necessary to sample this image in the field of Education. Abu Nasr Farabi placed a particularly strong emphasis on wisdom, ingenuity, within these qualities. Physical and mental qualities occupy an important place in the education of an Ideal person. He creates a human ideal that condemns his vile, filthy

qualities, exposes immoral personalities and gives them a noble moral, mature and perfect in all respects, and sets it as an example of the purpose of any education.

Within the great historical events that koehna Turan experienced, Amir Temur's idealized ideas and practical activities about justice are of great importance. Although he was ranked among the conquerors and experienced countless battles and intensities, his main goal was to establish justice. The Grand Commander held his state in high regard with intelligence and legal justification.

The idea of national statehood and its positive impact on the development of peoples can be clearly seen on the example of independent Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan's policy on international cooperation, regional peace, interethnic harmony is the basis for stability. Raising a healthy, harmonious generation in every possible way to adulthood, raising young people in the spirit of the harmony of national and nationwide values is one of the priorities of state policy. In our opinion, without such an ideal activity, it is possible to achieve the goal set neither in the economic, nor in the social, nor in the spiritual sphere. Such a person is happy when he always does good in his heart. Even a small goal makes him start to do big things. The goal is not self-fulfilling. It requires great preparation, perseverance, effort, valorization of difficulties.

When we pay attention to the stages of the development of personality each stage of Social Development had to make fundamental turns in different aspects of the life of that society during its transition to the second.

Conclusion

Today, legal, moral and spiritual problems arise in life. For this reason, contradictions as a problem of interdependence between the doctor and the patient are increasingly occurring in the health care system. This plays a central role in learning the discipline more deeply and illuminating its moral aspects to students.

The future of Uzbekistan's ideal of national development consists in building a great state, implementing the goals of the people, instilling a national idea in the hearts and minds of young people, raising morale. The 3000-year conscious historical-cultural experience of mankind testifies to this. The need to educate mature people who can resist such situations, harmoniously mature in every possible way, presupposes the formation of an ideology that is in the interests of our people and society.

In the development of society, it is the necessary task of each of us to turn spirituality, religion, values into a vital reality.

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